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Indian Vet. J., August 2012, 89 (8) : 66 - 68

Development of Thyroid Gland in Buffalo

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(Received : 12-05-2011;

Accepted : 15-06-2011)

The embryonic development of thyroid gland was studied in hamster (Ackerman and Knouff, 1964) and dog (Hendrickx, 1964). But no information is available on development of thyroid gland in buffalo. Therefore, a comprehensive study on development of thyroid was undertaken in buffalo.

Materials and Methods

38 buffalo fetuses were used for the present study and their CRL (crown rump length) varied from 0.9 cm to 80.0 cm (26 days to 254 days). Buffalo fetuses of different gestational age were collected from non-descript buffaloes, sacrificed in and around Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh. The CRL was

measured as a curved line along the vertebral column between the most anterior parts of frontal bone to the base of the tail. The approximate age of the foetus was determined on the basis of their CRL by using Soliman's formulae (1975). After measuring the CRL, the small embryos of less than 6.0 cm CRL were fixed as a whole. From large embryos thyroid glands were dissected out and fixed in 10 percent neutral buffered formalin. The fixed tissues were processed for paraffin sections by acetone benzene schedule (Luna, 1968). The paraffin sections of 5-6 μ m were subjected to Mayer's haematoxylin and eosin for normal histomorphology, Gridley's method for reticular fibres.

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Fig 1. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) showing thyroid primordium (Th) developing Oesophagus (O), Trachea (Tr), Parathyroid (P3), Thymic primordium III (T3) and Aortic arch III (A3) - *Haematoxylin and Eosin x 200.*

Fig 2. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 19.5 cm CRL (115 days) showing developing thyroid follicles and follicular epithelium (F) and blood vessels (B) around the follicles - *Haematoxylin and Eosin x 400.*

Fig 3. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 31 cm CRL (143 days) showing active thyroid follicles (AF) with colloid substance (C) and parafollicular cells (P) - *Haematoxylin and Eosin x 400.*

Fig 4. Photomicrograph of 31 cm CRL (143 days) buffalo foetus showing distinct reticular fibers (R) in between follicles (F) of thyroid gland - *Gridley's x 400.*

Results and Discussion

In the present study 0.9 cm CRL (26 days) embryo was the youngest in which five pairs of pharyngeal pouches were noted between the brachial arches on the lateral wall of the pharyngeal entoderm. The last one of these (fifth) was small and appeared to be absorbed into the fourth pharyngeal pouch resulting in the formation of caudal pharyngeal pouch complex. The pharyngeal pouches in buffalo were numbered 1 to 4 in cephalo-caudal sequence. Similarly, Noden and De Lahunta (1985) in cattle

and Prasad and Singh (1990) in goat stated that the fifth pharyngeal pouch never attained the morphological value of a definite pouch.

In the present study, primordium of thyroid gland was first noted as a median diverticulum of the floor of the pharynx at 1.2 cm CRL (28 days). Histogenesis of thyroid gland began at about 2.5 cm CRL (40 days). At this stage, thyroid primordium showed two distinct lobes on either side of the developing trachea and they were connected by unpaired isthmus ventrally. The cords of entodermal cells from the

thyroid diverticulum eventually branched into isolated growths and they transformed into thyroid follicles. At this stage cells were darkly stained showing distinct nucleus. At 19.5 cm CRL (115 days) thyroid primordium showed formation of follicles and follicular epithelium. At this stage thyroid was highly vascular. This may facilitate entrance of thyroid hormones into the blood stream (Latshaw, 1987). In the present study, at 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) characteristic thyroid follicles with cuboidal epithelium were noted in thyroid of buffalo. At this stage distinct colloid substance was also observed in the follicles. These findings suggested that thyroid of buffalo was functional from the early foetal life for normal growth and developing of the embryo. Thyroxine cannot pass through the placenta and thyroid is capable of forming thyroxine by about 35 days or earlier and was functioning during the second trimester in ruminants. Formation of capsule around the gland was noticed from the surrounding mesenchyme at 19.5 cm CRL (115 days). This capsule was distinct at 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) and in later stages of development. In the present study reticular fibres were few and were in formative stage at 115 days of gestation. However, they were characteristically seen at 143 days and subsequent stages of development of thyroid in buffalo. In active follicles, cells were long columnar type facing toward the follicular cavity with basal ends resting on the basal lamina. Further, in active follicles colloid showed foamy, serrated appearance and large number of vacuoles on the peripheral part of the colloid. This is due to reabsorption and mobilization of colloid into the follicular cells under the influence of thyroid stimulating hormone (Banks, 1981). But cells of inactive follicles were cuboidal type and colloid was homogenous without any serrations and vacuoles.

The ultimobranchial bodies were incorporated into the thyroid gland at 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) and these cells positioned between the developing thyroid follicles and along the basement membrane of the follicles and these cells were termed as parafollicular cells. These cells can be easily distinguished midst of the substance of the thyroid by their large size and pale staining properties. These cells do not extend

in to the follicular lumen.

Thyroid follicles also contained darkly stained slender colloid cells which were dropped into the colloid of the follicles. Kelly *et al.* (1984) named these cells as Langendorff cells or colloid cells in thyroid of human. These cells are degenerating cells and may be sloughed into the lumen of the follicle, adding their contents, including nucleoproteins and proteolytic enzymes to the colloid in thyroid of human.

Summary

38 buffalo fetuses were used in the present study and their CRL ranged from 0.9 cm to 80.0 cm CRL. Thyroid primordium was noted as a median diverticulum of the floor of the pharynx at 1.2 cm CRL (28 days). At 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) thyroid primordium showed two distinct lobes and they were connected by unpaired isthmus. At 19.5 cm CRL (115 days) formation of thyroid follicles as well as follicular epithelium began and thyroid was highly vascular at this stage. At 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) thyroid follicles and follicular epithelium were distinct. At this stage colloid substance was distinct in thyroid follicles of buffalo. Many reticular fibers were also reported between the follicles at this stage.

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